

Laser versus UV photolysis : A comparative study with carbazole

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A comparative study of the photolysis of carbazole with N_2 laser and UV light has been described. UV light effects simple N,N' -dimerization, whereas with laser, the molecule gets cleaved, producing N,N' -biscarbazoyl, phenol and aniline, in higher yield.

UV photolysis of organic compounds has been a vast field of study. Recently, laser has been introduced as a source in organic photochemistry¹. But only a few reports are available on the laser vs UV comparative photochemical studies². Here, we report the photolysis of carbazole (1) under UV light and N_2 laser.

An ethanolic solution of carbazole, when irradiated by UV light, gave N,N' -biscarbazoyl (2) as the only product after 30 h, whereas irradiation by N_2 laser under the same condition gave three products, viz. 2, phenol and aniline after 8 h (Scheme 1). The identity of 2 has been established by spectral data, elemental analysis and by comparing with the reported data³.

Scheme 1

Experimental

An ethanolic solution (100 ml) of carbazole was irradiated with 125 W medium pressure mercury vapour lamp and with broad beam N_2 laser ($\lambda = 337.1$ nm, $\tau = 7 \times 10^{-9}$ s, pps = 20 Hz, peak power = ~150 kW) separately. The

progress of the reactions was monitored by tlc and the products were isolated by preparative tlc using SiO_2 as adsorbent, benzene as developer and iodine vapour as visualiser. The R_f values were found to be as follows : product 2, 0.77; carbazole, 0.86; aniline, 0.93; phenol, 0.67.

Product 2 : Yield: with UV lamp ~0.2 g, with laser ~0.4 g, m.p. 155° (Found : C, 86.44; H, 4.92; N, 8.15. $C_{24}H_{16}N_2$ calcd. for : C, 86.74; H, 4.81; N, 8.43%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3020, 1610, 1590, 1475, 1325, 1265, 1140, 990, 920, 740, 710 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) δ 6.81 (4H, m, ArH), 7.2–7.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.15 (4H, m, ArH); m/z 332 (M^+ , weak) 167, 166.

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